

Discourse on Disability and Development: A Critical Survey of Literature

Deba Ranjan Hota

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: May 06, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Disability, Inclusiveness, Human Development Index, Personhood, Human Difference</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4740958</p>	<p><i>The present study delves into the existing literature on disability and development available at international level in understanding the inclusion/exclusion of certain local rationale in formulation of these very concepts. The existing and available secondary resources literature have been explored and analysed. There have been gaps in understanding of these concepts at Global North and Global South level. In addition it has investigated the modern measuring parameter of disability at international forum, national and local level which brought new insights at epistemological level. The interconnection, overlaps of these issues at different international fora has serious implication for the incorporation of the disability discourse at policy level world over.</i></p>

Introduction

This article attempts to relocate the epistemological disagreements between understandings of disability, inclusivity, and community in the North and South globe. At the outset it is understood that hegemonic idea of the general understandings of disability and its related practices are just as all inclusive developments of worldwide turn of events or the dominated empire. By 'universals', it is presumed the discourse in historical as well as recent writing in the discourse of disability, that there are generally acknowledged, homogeneous understandings and interpretation of disability builds just as practices that can be applied to any setting on the world, independent of one's convictions or practices (Bezzina, 2018; Kalyanpur, 2015; Mills and Fernando, 2014; Tribe, 2014). These understandings are prescriptive in nature and firmly tied down to formats of normative and best practices that are utilized as a way to classify, systematize, and approach human contrasts (Campbell, 2011, 2015; Kalyanpur, 2015). Defined by researchers as 'Geo-disability templates' (Campbell, 2015: 69), these universals are commonly presented internationally as a major aspect of globalised world where the theme is based 'on the universalization of the speculations of human difference' (Artiles and Dyson, 2005: 40) as opposed to thoughts and perspectives that are situated in explicit geo-spatial epistemologies (Artiles and Dyson, 2005; Kalyanpur, 2015; Mills and Fernando, 2014). Always the empire had belief systems on disability constructs, practices, and ideas of resurgence that originate from the North and have their premise in explicit epistemologies and secured in colonial legacies (Titchkosky and Aubrecht, 2015; Tribe, 2014).

I contend that hegemonic ideas of the universals on disability are inseparably identified with the more extensive themes on universal notion of Human Development Index (HDI), where nations are evaluated on a few measures, continuum extending from low human advancement to exceptionally high human turn of events (United Nations Development Program [UNDP]. Progress is subsequently connected with the refinement of development, a processes which one hand disability related convictions and practices that are seen to be 'traditional/conventional', and at the opposite end are rehearses that mirror an increasingly dynamic comprehension of handicap, in case of comprehensive education. The idea of progress was overwhelmingly rights-based, neuro-diversity, or inclusive education and the development is upscale in the index. In this article, an attempt is made about these overarching construct of the universals in both the territories of disability and development, and their relationship in axis of how disability, person-hood, and inclusivity featured in constrictive manners, as these understanding pervades South.

The analysis explain and does not discredit an all inclusiveness that imagines, at base education for all, personal satisfaction, human rights, and all inclusive social insurance. The study state that the quest for universals and the procedure through which this vision is to be accomplished cannot be separated from the geopolitical and past settings inside which this theme is developed and contextualized. The ontological suppositions in state, the normalization of personal satisfaction, disability, and person-hood, fit in with the authority of the all inclusive that is established in the Empire (Cohen, 2014; Titchkosky and Aubrecht, 2015; Tribe, 2014), and are neither kind nor apolitical. Can we ask whose imagined vision is being sought after within

the layer of the universals here? Which epistemologies and methods of being central, and which epistemologies are given way in these ideas of the universal?

The survey examines the experiences of Kalyanpur and Rao who are instructors in India and now live and work in the Global North, having seen the exchange of disability related belief systems, develops and practiced in 1980s till date in India. They have experienced preparing in intercessions and procedures that instinctively did not give an impression of being a match to any situation, in any case, as frequently occurs with local epistemologies, they neither have conceptualized dissonance nor its fundamental reasons. As educators and researchers, they have come to emphatically accept that while weakness exists all over the place, developments of disability contrast by settings and can be seen uniquely located in the particular social or cultural setting inside which they are arranged (Barnes, Oliver and Barton, 2008; Taylor, 2008).

In the explanation that follows, the paper will scrutinize two key indicators that underlie the current universalizing deliberations on disability and development. The first is the idea of all inclusiveness of meanings of disability development, their practices and holistic education, and their transferability to any setting regardless of local understandings of state, inclusivity and group. Based on previous researches contend that the acts of all inclusive 'norm standard setting' and arranging of disability, commonly intrinsic in crafted by global organizations, are methods of forcing the colonial layout of understanding human differences (Cohen, 2014; Titchkosky and Aubrecht, 2015; Tribe, 2014). The second is the possibility of worldwide development that underlies these general codifications of disability and best practices.

Elusive Search for Universals

A growing body of evidence has observed the epistemological disharmony between current understandings of disability and the developments of human difference between the North and the South (Bezzina, 2018; Grech, 2011; Harry, 2020; Kalyanpur and Rao, 2015; Kozleski, Artiles and Waitoller, 2014). The foundations of this discussion can be followed back to the 1980s and '90s when a constant flow of disability related administrations and practices were sent out to nations in the Global South (see Baine, 1988, 1990; Kalyanpur, 1996; Price, 1994; Verna and Pershad, 1984). Overwhelmed by the de-institutionalization development in the North and the expanding center around comprehensive education and disability backing, a considerable lot of the practices were transplanted to the Global South with the thinking that on the off chance that they could spike change in the nations they intended to. This consistent development of disability related practices and constructs did not mull over the social, material, basic, or historical settings of the nations that they were transplanted to. The underlying focal point of this early discourse was on the social importance of these practices or the degree to which they were in consonance with the local cultural social setting (Kalyanpur, 1996; Price, 1994; Verma and Pershad, 1984). As disability manifest, labels, and began advancing toward the Global South, researchers started to address the practices, yet the philosophies and suspicions of these practices, and most explicitly the understood conviction that disability was an all inclusive universal notion (Miles, 2001; Rao, 2001; Rao, 2006). To be sure, prior researchers around there, for example, Miles tested 'Eurocentric conventionality' and the propensity to accept a unified, solid meaning of disability, caused to notice the way that developments of disability can be multiple and varied. Featuring these developments of disability were perspectives on the body, knowledge, or hypotheses of human child growth which were already established in various epistemologies. Lately researchers from parts of the South have pointed the problematic of utilizing the very term 'disability' as a way to comprehend and reveal translations of human contrasts in different settings.

Despite the fact that the underlying foundations of this discord stretch back a very long while with, for example, the Human Development Index , which expect an all inclusiveness of the desiderata of advancement , the discussion has taken on an increasingly resistant voice with the emerging significance of disability as a piece of the plan at international domain. Ongoing funding demonstrates that the endeavors of global associations and donor organizations to force the utilization of 'geo-disability templates' to characterize the builds of disability, inclusivity and community, while benevolent, had problematises the situation.(Kalyanpur and Rao, 2015; Maudslay, 2014; Nguyen and Mitchell, 2014; Soldatic, et al., 2018). Campbell contends that intrinsic in these 'geo-disability templates' is the assumption of all inclusive frameworks and standard setting that can 'bring renegade states 'into line'. Further funding shows that these geo-disability layouts of disability related belief systems are presently bringing about new and disturbing dilemmas (see Maudslay, 2014; Nguyen and Mitchell, 2014; Soldatic et al., 2018), as examined later in this article.

The development towards prescriptive formats of disability and its related practices is arranged inside the more extensive authentic setting of global advancement that has yielded an agreement on what constitutes the development. The idea of the Human Development Index (HDI), which grades nations over a continuum of improvement extending from 'created' to 'creating' (Ajmera, 2016; Harber, 2014; Kalyanpur, 2014; Singal, Lynch and Johanssen, 2019) is established in the post-World War II setting. The accomplishment of the Marshall (European Recovery Program), whereby financial guide was occupied to help the recuperation and remaking of Western Europe, turned into the catalyst for comparative recuperation endeavors in numerous nations in Asia and Africa. The suspicion that these previous states ought to be guided towards a model of advancement characterized by the west prompted the making of a system of money related and specialized help

from generally previous forces to their previous settlements, which was systematized through the United Nations in offices, for example, UNESCO, UNICEF, and UNDP. While the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund give financial guide essentially, offices like UNESCO and UNICEF additionally give specialized help with the type of experts and experts from the Global North who present governments and NGOs in the worldwide South. The monetary aid, the provincial history of this relationship, and the general notion of development, act harmoniously together to advance the exportation of 'universal' Northern disabilities belief systems and practices.

Albeit arranged in western thoughts of financial development, the HDI in the beginning intended to go past carefully monetary markers, like total national output and gross national item and towards increasingly far reaching proportions of development, in the case of education, health, human rights, and access to resources. Unmistakably expressing that 'the reason for development is to offer individuals more alternatives', the report's own motivation was 'neither to lecture nor to suggest a specific model of development' and recognized that 'any effectively carved out procedure must mirror the varying view of developed and developing countries' related to the Sustainable Development Goals 2030, set by the World Bank and other global offices, in addition settled the courses for these objectives to be reached. Further, the review contend, the meaning of the guidelines for all inclusive turn of events, the link among donor and beneficiaries, and bringing lagging nations up to these principles, is characteristic of the Empire in view of neo-colonial globalization. The inclination to arrange templates of development in the binaries of traditional versus modernity has become a way to get control over the distinctions marked by the colonial gaze on the 'other' (Fanon, 1961; Said, 1979; Tlostanova and Mignolo, 2012). The division of tradition and modernity, transparent in the early endeavors of the colonizers, is less apparent in what Tlostanova and Mignolo intends to as the 'rhetoric of salvation', where the contemporary construction of development has become an amazing way to delete indigenous and local epistemologies, respecting unique sorts of information and consigning others to the edge. This oppressiveness is manifested in the exchange of disability related belief systems (Grech, 2015a; Soldatic et al., 2018), where the colonial are reframing' of disability and bodies esteemed as the 'other', presently proceeds through the globalization of the biomedical model and associations like the World Health Organization which is the arm of this model (Mills and Fernando, 2014; Tribe, 2014). To cite a case in point WHO manuals and files, the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health have become the devices for the normalization and universalization of human difference (Mills and Fernando, 2014; Titchkosky and Aubrecht, 2015; Tribe, 2014). In the segments beneath, I have investigated the presence of the empire in three explicit zones: the language of disability, understandings of personhood, and ideas of inclusivity.

Many Researchers have noticed that the term disability itself is an English expression with social, cultural, historical, and etymological roots established in the Global North. This discussion has not included the examination of the semantics of the term, yet the discussion encompassing this term inside the North, further shows the unique epistemological base of this term, the issues characterizing, and the key role that the English language plays in building up this epistemology. Why would that be hurry to trade the widespread design of disability when the very idea of all inclusiveness regarding how we develop human difference is being tested over and again inside the Global North, the setting in which it originates? Here, Rao contends that there has been a propensity to utilize western ideas of disability to reveal disability related history in non-western settings, resulting in an interpretation of disability history that is fundamentally the same as the context of origin. At the point when arranged in a double as found in the Global North, disability turns into the characterizing normal for the individual, that is, one is either disabled or not. Furthermore, the presence of a disability with regards to the Global North is understood as disparaging, proposing that being autistic is seen as less attractive than being neurotypical; in spite of the way that chemical imbalance in this situation is being seen as a vital part of human diversity, variety and identity, as opposed to a shortcoming. On the other hand, the specific terms used to depict human differences in specific bits of the Global South, may not so much have a dividing negating post, and thus not portray human complexities in combine. Further, there might be already existing terms that are a part of the local language and used in a variety of contexts to describe multiple situations.

Personhood, Intellect, and Human Differences: Erasure in Embeddedness

Naturally identified with language are notions of personhood, faculty, and human differences. While a few researchers have highlighted the robustness of the universal classifying proof and arrangement frameworks for disability and working created by the World Health Organization and the Washington Group (Florian et al., 2006; Singal, Lynch and Johannsen, 2019), others contend that it depends on a nosology of sickness that is established in the clinical viewpoint (Campbell, 2015; Titchkosky and Aubrecht, 2015). Intrinsic in these orders, are perspectives on the body and methods of conceptualizing disability that are established in Northern epistemological locale and in ideas of normativity and classification that show an unmistakable discord with local constructions. The thought of an all inclusive standard as far as bodies and psyches is a lot of obvious in the manuals; this, amusingly, while the discourse in critical disability studies contemplates questions the developments of the norms and standards and analyzes the places of benefit and force that underlie the meaning of these norms. These layouts benefit the Northern viewpoints of human difference and ignore the nuanced

translations of disability that prevail in the South. Utilizing parallel developments of the human body, intellect, and other human contrasts, gets tricky in settings where identity is complex, consistently moving, and hybrid. Current discussions on basic social equity and intersectional viewpoints inside the Global North cause to notice the significance of understanding at local context. However, before we even get to characterizing mistreatment and appearances of ableness (ism), we have to see how personhood is developed inside regions in the Global South. What are vernacular understandings of personhood, humanness, or ability, and how would they converge with position, class, and a person's place in the family, sex, and age inside the growing canvas of globalization?

Inclusivity and Community: Incompatible Binary

Inclusive education and training has been a on the rise for instructive change since the mid 1980s in a great part of the Global North, where children with disabilities were generally barred from schools. Basic to this themes are notion of social justice, human rights, equity, and access (Artiles, Harris-Murri and Rostenberg, 2006; Kozleski, Artiles and Waitoller 2014), testing the conventional role that schools have played in perpetrating disparities. With the notable Salamanca Statement on comprehensive instruction that was marked by 92 governments and 25 global associations in 1994 at the World Conference on Special Needs Instruction, comprehensive education started to saturate worldwide approach reports on education. As it may, the education planted the idea without local, contextual, logical underpinnings have carried the risk of idiosyncrasy within it. Drawing on the discoveries of an ethnographic examination that concentrated on the points of view of educators, scholastics, and teachers and trainers in Bogota, Colombia, Kamenopoulou expounds on the special manners by which consideration is deciphered when transplanted to settings in the Global South. Again he contends that these understandings of comprehensive instruction by educators do not think about the specific context of Colombia. The interpretation of inclusive education practiced in Colombia mirrors the same situation as of South. In spite of the fact that the talk in the approach centers around incorporation, by and by the convictions reflects a biomedical model where consideration is seen as being contingent and weakness is viewed as situated inside the disabled student.

Richard depicts how comprehensive and inclusive education in Ladakh is unraveling as driving the students from their families and putting them in lodging or an institutional setting, which is far away from their homes. This lodging, albeit proposed to be a 'comprehensive setting', turns into a setting where families who cannot deal with their youngster 'can relieve' themselves of caretaking burdens'. In contrast to the United States, Ladakh is a nation that does not have a background marked by institutionalization of individuals with disabilities. Comparative idiosyncratic translations of holistic and all inclusive education like this have created in different parts of the Global South. Kalyanpur states that in spite of the challenge to double frameworks in the Northern theme on inclusive education, without any tutoring for children with disabilities, inclusive education in India is for the most part seen as an equal arrangement of lone choices. While the current writing here noticed the calculated hindrances to actualizing comprehensive instruction, the discord that exists between these worldwide template and local epistemologies remain generally un-examined. How do these worldwide designs of incorporation meet with settings where implications of community, inclusivity and consideration are intricate and secured or arranged to collectivist systems?

At the center of our understandings of integration and inclusivity is the thought of community, a term that has been distinguished by researchers as having epistemological origins in the North. Vital to this definition are physical or allegorical spaces that individuals from a community are consigned to, notions of inclusion and exclusion and valued or devalued role ascribed or attributed to the individuals from the community. Depicting the chronicled setting for the roots of the term, Lawthom and Whelan note that developments of community in the Global North incorporate community as a place, included individuals who live in proximity to each other, individuals who share common interests and bonds, and a 'lot of morals, values and behavioral'. Specifically, the word has profound epistemological roots and cannot be separated from the concept of community base integration and the historical backdrop of deinstitutionalization of individuals with disabilities in the Global North. Especially inside the setting of community based integration, the thought of living inside the community had all the more a spatial meaning, an understanding that in this manner went under critical scrutiny (Bogdan and Taylor, 1989a, 1989b). The approach of reconciliation development in the United States during the 1970s finished in the dislocating of individuals with handicaps from large isolated foundations to small settings regularly alluded to as group homes. In spite of the fact that group homes were truly situated in the network, this adjustment in area without anyone else did not really ensure that individuals with disability were genuinely a part of commune. Features of being members of community, for example, having valuable role, keeping up a variety of relationship, participating in the community, being present in communities in the community in different ways were fundamentally missing. Rather, studies found the loneliness overwhelmingly in the lives of individuals with disability, in spite of the way of community reconciliation. The limited understanding of community was then extended to incorporate the valued roles that individuals occupy in the community and the

kind of relationships that individuals have, the kind of exercises that individuals take part in, and how their membership is construed.

Inside the social, cultural, historical setting of India, the meaning of community is unpredictable and goes beyond mere physical space or closeness. Rather, making of personhood and community membership incorporate sexual orientation, position, class, kinship role, enrollment in the family hierarchy, and ties started from birth and created and sustained by marriage. Anand contends that inside the South Asia a comprehension of how mortal bodies cross with conventional ideas of space is basic to developing an individual's personhood and the position they occupy in the community. Since distancing practices and notions of purity are vital to the caste framework, she opines is a significant piece of deciphering human contrasts. Caste position, personhood, and disability converge in manners that an individual with disabilities from a 'high caste' would have more access to a community and a more grounded stronger feeling of having a place than an person with disability from a 'lower caste,' just by virtue of their standing in caste status. Additionally, the builds and ethos, the idea of relationship that is vital to supporting a community and the inherent desires to keeping up these connections are similarly paradoxical. While the duality of inclusion/ exclusion and oppressor/oppressed, one may contend, are available in a community of any kind, despite the context, the nuanced and complex manners by which they show themselves may not be deciphered through the duality from the North. Undoubtedly, understanding the experience of being included, abused, or in any event, involving an undecided situation in the community might be shrouded until one sees how that community is built and how the different positions of benefit and marginalisation converge to make new areas that attribute value, personhood, or community participation through membership to a person (Harry, 2020; Kozleski, Artiles and Waitoller, 2014). With this viewpoint is likewise the way that positions of advantage and marginalization may be fluid and rely upon an individual's age, gender, changing roles in the family, and other variables.

Latest inquiries into the unpredictability of identity and personhood in communitarian societies reveals solitary features alone may not be sufficient to comprehend the position and privilege of specific individuals in the family and community. Inside the Indian setting, female identities are viewed as auxiliary to that of their children, where being a mother of a kid with an intellectual incapacity adds another aspect to the role. John and Bailey found that Gujarati mothers of kids with intellectual disabilities considered there to be needs as equivalent to their child's, proposing that the personality of the kid and the mother were fundamentally joined. They contend that mother of kids with a scholarly inability are set in a position where they become advocates for their kid and need to arrange in one. These selves incorporate the bigger cultural desires for providing care related with being mothers alongside the self that they need to build given the experience of child rearing a youngster with a mental handicap. Accordingly, their identities are constantly being built and remade dependent on their gender, their role as as mother, just as being mother of youngsters with intellectual disability. The intersection of gender and disability manifested in marriage, which is indispensably connected with constructions of being a woman, is especially an issue and frequently out of reach for women with disability in certain pieces of the South. In this manner, inside the Global South, notions of handicap are perplexing and cannot be isolated from the bigger collectivist structures inside which identity is construed.

Again, identified with the understandings of inclusivity and ideas of community, is likewise that a community receives to incorporate or bar its members. Within the Global North, this basic talk has concentrated on a rights-based language so as to propel social policy, educational organizations, and local community to provide and be comprehensive. What might be the idea of this discussion in the frame of the epistemological understandings of community? Rao's study, gives the case of two Bengali mothers of child with critical disabilities who encouraged consideration for their child in their local neighborhood and more extended families. In any case, rather than utilizing a rights-based methodology, the mothers utilized an awareness raising methodology that evoked the *manushatto* inside the excluders and perceived the humankind of the person they were barring. Established in this methodology, was a talk that concentrated on inspiring superficial understandings of family and kinship role, building ties of *bhalobasha*, and getting individuals to ponder their *babohar*. From various perspectives, the mothers were upholding for a way to deal with incorporation that went past unimportant consistence and required awareness of one's musings and deliberately picking activities that rose up out of an internal space of quality and care as opposed to ones which were trigger responses to a disposition uncritically sprang up from society. Dissimilar to the Northern talk on rights that is enacted by supporters and activists who utilize the social equity structure, this methodology is an instructional one which perceives that relationship are complementary and must be persistently characterized and re-imagined so as to grapple them in their basic roots. In an ethnographic study on members in the Immortelle Children's Center in Trinidad, Harry states that styles of advocacy in parts of the Global South, for example, Trinidad are arranged in community setting where design are more personalistic than legalistic.

Based on a study that focused on the narratives of six mothers of children with disability in South Africa, Muthukrishna and Ebrahim argues that understandings of disability in the Global South contended that during the time spent grasping a human rights approach out of a Global North point of view, 'issues basic to socio-cultural and political contexts of the South have been ignored in research, and the social and material real

factors of the lives of disabled and their families in the South stay under-theorized'. They underscore that, so as to comprehend developments of disability and community, we have to see how guardians build their role and is arranged within the context of the social relations inside the community. The mothers in this experiment encouraged the consideration of their children by opposing the predominant design on disability that concentrated on stigma and disgrace. Turning rather to the indigenous backings for incorporation of their kid that were accessible in their families and communities, they tackled the ethic of 'Ubuntu,' a quality reflected in a person that has a 'sense of community, empathy and shared concern for the rights of others'. The changes in North incorporate the expanding consideration of individuals with inabilities and a solid accentuation on self-advocacy and self-assurance. The ideas of strengthening and self-advocacy as imagined in the west, do not lean themselves to a shortsighted exchange to the Global South. Further, dissimilar to western landscape of self-advocacy where the person with disability has the essential state agencies and the decision and control of services, in India, the family despite everything assumes a key role. In the Global South, the talk on rights might be restricted to a few elite, and be generally out of reach for individuals with handicaps who are poor and disenfranchised as a result of other structural disparities (see Grech, 2015a; Kalyanpur and Rao, 2015).

Conclusion

The discourse on disability and development is attached to an epistemic viewpoint that is deep in the colonial roots of the Empire. The search for the universals, the tendency to denote and demarcate human differences, the use of language to label and categorize the bodies of the other, are related to a colonial psyche. The developing prejudice of ambiguities in how human difference could be built upon and the expanding disharmony made by the uncritical investigation of Northern disability philosophies, require a change in deduction and practice leading to new transformation. At the center of this discord which can be explained as follows. To begin with, if change needs to come, the guarantee lies in what Tlostanova and Mignolo portray as 'border thinking'. Border thinking, as they depict it, alludes to a specific position that is 'grounded in the encounters of the colonies and subaltern empires'. The opportunity has come to move past the post-colonial system to decolonization of thoughts, philosophies, and practices established in the authority of northern epistemic perspectives on human contrasts. The 'epistemic locus' must be the information and encounters of individuals in the local context. Situating oneself in the outskirts can be a key way to decolonize how we consider disability and development, including testing the matrix of power that be, and respecting indigenous familiarities that offer an alternative edge of comprehension. As have been referenced else, the ramifications of this are to perceive that there are local understanding of human differences and local rehearses that have worked for an explanation, and which reveal these local translations of disability and related human contrasts.

Second, captivating in neocolonial thinking implies investigating extensive perspectives about bodies and psyches that are hybrid, and possess the less known and frequently undetectable spaces between the prevailing models. This implies opposing the propensity to surrender to engulf colonial constructions by naming these spaces as characteristic of a restricted progress'. It implies an intense feeling of mindfulness that knows about imperialism which focuses on 'creating and sharpening our reasoning procedure and pursuing after politics for transformative change'. Third, on a sober level, there is a need to recognize alternatives based structures of reasoning that regards local strengths and indigenous knowledge of disability and disability related practices that have created in light of local needs and local reasons. This implies looking at the relevant and worldly gaps that exist between proposed manner of speaking and genuine usage of disability related practices in the Global South and understanding the historical, cultural, structural and material context of these nations (Kozleski, Artiles and Waitoller, 2014; Harry, 2020). Kozleski, Artiles and Waitoller express that there is a propensity to accept that marginalization happens in one-dimensional and universal ways as opposed to perceiving that there are complex and intersectional aspects of marginalization just as multiple manners by which personhood is constructed. Accordingly, practices like advocacy and inclusivity may metamorphose themselves distinctively in collectivist context where relationships are important rather than an individualist stance.

References

- Ajmera, M. (2016). *Invisible children: Reimagining international development at the grassroots*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Anand, S. (2015). Corporeality and culture: Theorizing difference in the South Asian context. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp.154-170). New York: Peter Lang.
- Artiles, A. J. & Dyson, A. (2005). Inclusive education in the globalization age: The Promise of comparative cultural historical analysis. In D. Mitchell (ed.). *Contextualizing inclusive education* (pp. 37-62). London: Routledge.
- Artiles, A.J., Harris-Murri, N. & Rostenberg, D. (2006). Inclusion as social justice: critical notes on discourses, assumptions, and the road ahead. *Theory into practice*, 45(3), 260- 268.

- Azzopardi, A. (2012). Spaces for inclusive communities: Reflections on contemporary society. In A. Azzopardi & S. Grech (eds.), *Inclusive communities: A critical reader* (pp.41-54). Netherlands: Sense Publishers.
- Baine, D. (1988). *Handicapped children in developing countries: Assessment, curriculum and instruction*. Alberta, Canada: University of Alberta Printing Services.
- Baine, D. (1990). Guide to the development, evaluation, and/or adoption or modification of tests for early childhood education in developing countries. In K. Marfo & M. J. Thorburn (eds.). *Practical approaches to childhood disability in developing countries: Insights from experience and research* (pp. 199-224). St. John's, Newfoundland: Memorial University, Project SEREDEC.
- Barnes, C., Oliver, M. & Barton, L. (2008). Introduction. In C. Barnes, M. Oliver & L. Barton (eds.). *Disability studies today* (pp. 1–17). Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.
- Bezzina, L. (2018). The role of indigenous and external knowledge in development interventions with disabled people in Burkina Faso: the implications of engaging with lived experiences. *Disability and the Global South*, 5(2), 1488-1507.
- Bogdan, R. & Taylor, S.J. (1989a). On accepting relationships between people with mental retardation and non-disabled people: towards an understanding of acceptance. *Disability, Handicap & Society*, 4(1), 21–35.
- Bogdan, R. & Taylor, S. J. (1989b). Relationships with severely disabled people: The social construction of humanness. *Social Problems*, 36, 135–148.
- Bost, S. (2019). Disability, decoloniality, and other-than-humanist ethics in Anzaldúan thought. *Disability and the Global South*, 6(1), 1562-1580.
- Breidlid, A. (2013). *Education, Indigenous Knowledges, and Development in the Global South: Contesting Knowledges for a Sustainable Future*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Campbell, F.K. (2011). Geodisability knowledge production and international norms: A Sri Lankan case study. *Third World Quarterly*, 32(8), 1455–1474.
- Campbell, F.K. (2015). The terrain of disability law in Sri Lanka: Obstacles and possibilities for change. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp.73-98). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Chatterjee, P. (1993). *The nation and its fragments: Colonial and postcolonial histories*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Dei, G.J.S. & Jaimungal, C.S. (2018). Indigeneity and decolonial resistance: An introduction. In G.J.S. Dei & C. S. Jaimungal (eds.). *Indigeneity and decolonial resistance: Alternatives to colonial thinking and practice* (pp.13-28). Gorham, ME: Myers Education Press.
- Fanon, F. (1961) *The Wretched of the Earth*. London: Penguin.
- Florian, L., Hollenweger, J. et al. (2006). Cross-Cultural Perspectives on the Classification of Children with Disabilities: Part I. Issues in the Classification of Children with Disabilities. *The Journal of Special Education*, 40(1), p. 36–45.
- Grech, S. (2011). Recolonising debates or perpetuated coloniality? Decentring the spaces of disability, development and community in the global south. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 15(1), 87-100.
- Grech, S. (2015a). *Disability and Poverty in the Global South: Renegotiating Development in Guatemala*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Grech, S. (2015b). Decolonizing Eurocentric disability studies: why colonialism matters in the disability and global South debate. *Social Identities*, 12(1), 6-21.
- Harber, C. (2014). *Education and International Development: Theory, Practice and Issues*. Oxford, UK: Symposium Books
- Harry, B. (2020). *Childhood Disability, Advocacy, and Inclusion in the Caribbean: A Trinidad and Tobago Case Study*. Switzerland: Springer Nature.
- Husain, S. & Sanders, E. B.-N. (2012). Fusion of horizons: Co-designing with Cambodian children who have prosthetic legs, using generative design tools. *Co Design*, 8(1), 43– 79.
- John, A. & Bailey, L. E. (2017). Multiple selves: Gujarati women's narratives of mothering a child with an intellectual disability. *Narrative Inquiry*, 27(2), 357-377.
- Kozleski, E., Artiles, A. & Waitoller, F. (2014). Equity in inclusive education: A cultural historical comparative perspective. In L. Florian (ed.). *The Sage Handbook of Special Education, volume 1*. (p. 231-250). Los Angeles: Sage.
- Kalyanpur, M. (1996). The Influence of Western Special Education on Community-based Services in India. *Disability and Society*, 11(2), 249–270.
- Kalyanpur, M. (2008). Equality, quality and quantity: challenges in inclusive education policy and service provision in India. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 12(3), 243- 262.

- Kalyanpur, M. (2009). Cultural variations on the construction of self-advocacy in the context of India. In M. Alur & V. Timmons (eds.), *Inclusive education across cultures: crossing boundaries, sharing ideas* (pp. 332-341). Sage Publications
- Kalyanpur, M. (2014). Distortions and dichotomies in inclusive education for children with disabilities in Cambodia in the context of globalization and international development. *International Journal of Disability, Development, and Education*, 61(1), 80-94.
- Kalyanpur, M. (2015a). Mind the gap: Special education policy and practice in India in the context of globalization. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp.49-72). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Kalyanpur, M. & Rao, S. (2015b). Conclusion. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp. 289-304). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Kalyanpur, M. (in press) Inclusive and special education in Asia. In U. Sharma & S. Salend (eds.). *Oxford encyclopedia of inclusive and special education*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Kamenopoulou, L. (2018). Inclusive education in the Global South? A Colombian perspective: 'When you look towards the past, you see children with disabilities, and if you look towards the future, what you see is diverse learners'. *Disability and the Global South*, 5(1), 1192-1214.
- Lawthom, R. & Whelan, P. (2012). Understanding Communities. In A. Azzopardi & S. Grech (eds.). *Inclusive communities: A critical reader* (pp.11-22). Netherlands: Sense Publishers
- Le Fanu, G. (2015). Imagining disability? Conceptualizations of learners with disabilities and their learning in the pedagogic manuals of international development agencies. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 40, 267-275.
- Lovett, H. (1996). *Agnes: People who hurt themselves*. Baltimore: Brookes Publishing.
- Mairs, N. (1986). On being a cripple. *The Lame Dame*. Available at: <http://thelamedame.tumblr.com/post/30938417648/on-being-a-cripple> retrieved on June 12, 2020
- Mehrotra, N. & Vaidya, S. (2013). Exploring constructs of intellectual disability and personhood in Haryana and Delhi. In R. Addlakha (ed.). *Disability Studies in India: Global Discourses and Local Realities* (pp.145-168). New Delhi: Routledge.
- Meekosha, H. (2008). Contextualizing disability: developing southern/global theory. Keynote paper presented at the 4th Biennial Disability Studies Conference, Lancaster University, UK.
- Miles, M. (1992). Concepts of Mental Retardation in Pakistan: Towards Cross-cultural and Historical Perspectives. *Disability and Society*, 7(3), 235–255.
- Miles, M. (2001). Studying Responses to Disability in South Asian Histories: Approaches personal, practical and pragmatical. *Disability & Society*, 16(1), 143–160.
- Mills, C. & Fernando, S. (2014). Globalizing mental health or pathologizing the Global South? Mapping the ethics, theory and practice of global mental health. *Disability and the Global South*, 1(2), 188-202.
- Mount, B. (2000). *Person-centered planning: Finding directions for change using personal futures planning*. New York: Graphic Futures Inc.
- Mukherjee, S. (2016). *The Gene: An Intimate History*. New York: Scribner.
- Muthukrishna, N. & Ebrahim, H. (2014). Motherhood and the disabled child in the contexts of early education and care. *Childhood*, 21(3), 369-384.
- Nguyen, X.T. & Mitchell, C. (2014). Inclusion in Vietnam: An intersectionality perspective on girls with disabilities and education. *Childhood*, 21(3), 324-338.
- Price, P. (1994). Early intervention in the South Pacific: Issues in program development. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 41(3), 223-230.
- Price, M. (2011). *Mad at school: Rhetoric's of mental disability and academic life*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan.
- Rao, S. (2001). 'A Little Inconvenience': Perspectives of Bengali families of children with disabilities on labeling and inclusion. *Disability and Society*, 16(4), 531-548.
- Rao, S. (2006). Parameters of normality and cultural constructions of 'mental retardation': Perspectives of Bengali families. *Disability & Society*, 21(2), 159–178.
- Rao, S. (2015a). Charting the landscape of disability studies in South Asia. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp. 18-48). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Rao, S. (2015b). Colloquial language and disability: Local Contexts and implications for inclusion. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp. 171-196). New York, NY: Peter Lang.
- Rao, S. (2015c). 'Just a member of the neighborhood': Bengali mothers' efforts to facilitate inclusion for their children with disabilities within local communities. In S. Rao & M. Kalyanpur (eds.). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons* (pp. 224- 245). New York, NY: Peter Lang.

- Rao, S. & Kalyanpur, M. (2015). *South Asia and Disability Studies: Redefining boundaries and extending horizons*. New York: Peter Lang.
- Richard, B. O. (2014). Families, well-being, and inclusion: Rethinking priorities for children with cognitive disabilities in Ladakh, India. *Childhood*, 21(3), 308-323.
- Said, E. (1979). *Orientalism*. New York, NY: Random House.
- Sensoy, O. & Di Angelo, R. (2012). *Is everyone really equal: An introduction to key concepts in social justice education?* New York, NY: Teachers College Press.
- Singal, N., Salifu, E.M. et al. (2015). The impact of education on shaping lives: Reflections of young people with disabilities in Ghana. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 19(9), 908-925.
- Singal, N., Lynch, P. & Johansson, S.T. (2019) Education of children with disabilities: Changing landscape of new opportunities and challenges .In N. Singal, P. Lynch. & S.T. Johansson (eds.). *Education and disability in the global South: New perspectives from Africa and Asia*. (pp. 1-18). London, UK: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Soldatic, K. & Biyanwila, J. (2006). Disability and development: A critical southern standpoint on able-bodied masculinity. In TASA 2006 Conference Proceedings, TASA Conference, University of Western Australia & Murdoch University, 2006, pp.1-12.
- Soldatic, K., Melhoe, L. et al. (2018). Challenges in global Indigenous–Disability comparative research, or, why nation-state political histories matter. *Disability and the Global South*, 5(2), 1450-1471.
- Stanton, E. (2007). The human development index: A history. Working paper series, 127. University of Massachusetts, Amherst.
- Taylor, S. (2008). Before it had a name: Exploring the historical roots of disability studies in Education available on <https://disabilitystudies.syr.edu/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/BeforeIt-Had-a-Name-Taylor-1.pdf> retrieved on 12 July 2020

Author Information

Dr. Deba Ranjan Hota

works in IMPRESS Project, ICSSR, Institute of Law,
NIRMA University, Ahmedabad
